

An assessment on quarter-life crisis of selected young professionals: Basis in the development of employee wellness program

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Abstract

This study assessed the quarter-life crisis of selected young professionals, if there is a significant correlation on the perceived levels of quarter-life crisis-related factors, and the perceptions of the respondents when grouped according to the demographic profile using a mixed method. This study revealed that the demographic profile of the respondents, age, and highest educational attainment, has no significance on the quarter-life crisis of young professionals. But there is a correlation among factors like anxiety, job dissatisfaction, financial instability, and difficulty in social relationship as these increased when the respondents faced the crisis in life. There is a correlation in job dissatisfaction and financial instability when one of them increases. The correlation between job dissatisfaction and social relationships is not significant, and the correlation between financial stability and social relationships is not significant either.

Keywords: *Quarter-life crisis, professionals, development, employee, wellness program.*

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Introduction

Growing up is not easy at all. Whether we like it or not, people go through transitions from childhood to adulthood. Switching to adult roles is a little bit scary for others due to major changes since "adulthood" is quite challenging. Nowadays, a lot of people entering in adulthood commonly have feelings of anxieties and inadequacies in making the most of opportunities before settling down because of too much pressure about finding themselves and getting their wants and full of uncertainties with their goals and plans. Unlike the older generations that did not have to deal with it so much. Sadly, this generation of young adults is experiencing a quarter-life crisis. This will prove that young adults or the working millennials today are prone to stresses and are not exempted from the struggles and circumstances in this phase of life. Luckily, some people are happy and blessed because they know exactly what they want in life while others are not. A quarter-life crisis is becoming more common because so many people slowly letting go of their hopes and dreams and become so unsure about their future.

The quarter-life crisis involves insecurity, self-doubt, disappointment in terms of a person's financial status, relationship, and profession and sometimes involves depression related to general feelings of anxieties. A quarter-life crisis can usually begin at the age of twenties (20's) to thirties (30's). This age range tends to be the best life for some people but for most people, this tends to be the age that they will respond to a quarter-life crisis, feeling under pressure to succeed by rushing

things in life such as finding a career they are passionate about and fulfill them somehow, becoming financially independent, owning properties like dream house and fancy car, maintaining flourishing relationships and friendships, marriage and having children, making choices and making long-term personal or professional decisions while all of these can cause a lot of insecurities. The fact that all these also were not achievable for most people. This could be the age that some people feel they are not achieving their full potential, or they achieve nothing despite their hard works, and they are falling behind. They feel unhappy and not living up their lives like they are waiting for life to begin and start to develop a positive outlook in life when they realize that some people of their age have accomplished a lot. A quarter-life crisis concentrates on the frustration of hopelessness and perceived lack of fulfillment in life. It often results in deciding of which direction a person will be headed for.

Having a quarter-life crisis can make young adults strive to achieve work and life balance. They begin to care about what the world thinks about them. Their strengths and weaknesses are not clear enough for them. They are feeling down all the time and have an emotional sad aura, lost lonely soul while questioning their goals, their purpose, and their contribution every moment of their lives. A quarter-life crisis can lead young adults to low self-esteem and dissatisfaction of living especially if it is not the ideal life. Having a quarter-life crisis can make young adults doubt their choices up to their present situation. They are lacking a sense of direction and they are trying to change the path of their lives (De Leon, 2011).

According to Erik H. Erikson's (1950) intimacy versus isolation, the sixth stage of psychosocial development, people tend to be with people who have the same identity to have a proper relationship with them. If they do not establish a concrete relationship with others, it will lead to depression. Erikson's conception of early adulthood has been modernized by Arnett's work which theorized about emerging adulthood. As clearly argued, emerging adulthood is a procedure of developing skills, capabilities, capacities, and qualities of character deemed by their cultures as necessary for completing the transition to adulthood of the young adult. This is a depressive stage of life in which emerging adults can also lead to depression. This quarter-life crisis leads conduct to stress, anxiety, and depression.

According to Johnson (2017) as cited by ABS-CBN News (2018), it shows that 61% of young adults experienced a quarter-life crisis because they are unsure of their career choices and compare themselves with successful friends or people they know that causes the feeling of anxiety. The data further shows that 36% of 25 to 33 years old are job changers. They switch to new industries and new roles. According to their research, they found that people are looking for career advice but do not know what they want, while others do not have the right connections.

As reported by LinkedIn (2017), among Asian countries, India has the highest rate of young professionals who experience a quarter-life crisis with a staggering 89.9%, followed by Philippines with 87.5% and Hong Kong with 87.2%, then Singapore with 82.9%. The greatest issue weighing in the minds of young professionals in those countries that develop large cases of the quarter-life crisis was finding a job or career that they are passionate about. Another issue is comparing themselves with friends they deem more successful than they are. The ability to afford their dream lifestyle and finding a compatible life partner is also another growing issue for young professionals.

As stated in The Manila Times (2018), in the Philippines almost 87% of Filipinos aged 25-33 years old are experiencing a quarter-life crisis. They have a concept on what their dream career

would be but do not know how to achieve getting it as they are trapped in their current career due to financial status and wants advice on how to deal with it. They feel no one can help them in their predicament, especially someone who can help them get out of the situation.

Methods

The researchers used the Qualitative – Quantitative (Mixed Method) for their Research Design, which means that the researchers collected, analyzed, and integrated the survey (quantitative) and interviews (qualitative) approached in data gathering. The researchers' highlighted the different factors of Quarter-Life Crisis and the extent participants were affected by it, by the age range of 20s to 30s. Moreover, they will assess the success of the wellness program by assessing the needs of the participants, as in perspectives will be gathered in the likes of job satisfaction, financial difficulties, among others. The respondents of this study will be selected individuals with a quarter-life crisis. Through purposive sampling, the respondents will undergo assessment in identifying a quarter-life crisis. Once identified, they were considered as the reliable respondents of the study. The respondents will be identified through their demographic profile such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, and employment status.

The research used the Carol Ryff's (1989) wellbeing scale, a test to determine the existence of a quarter-life crisis as the test measures aspects of wellbeing and happiness: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance.

The researchers administered a self-made test that measures the job satisfaction, anxiety, social relationship, financial status, and commitment to the organization. This was rated by the subject matter experts who conducted the reliability test. The researchers interviewed the respondents with a set of selected validated questions to give more qualitative data from the respondents on the hypothesized, as well as the un-hypothesized factors and variables concerning the quarter-life crisis.

The researchers handed a wellbeing scale of Carol Ryff to a group of respondents to gather data pertinent to their quarter-life crisis. Then the researchers divided the respondents into equal groups by their sex, age, highest educational attainment, and employment status by the process of T-Test. The researchers provided to the respondents the self-made test to determine the factors of the quarter-life crisis.

Results and Analysis

Table 1. Mean Score for Anxiety Factor per Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variables	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	49.69	High in Anxiety
	Female	51.36	High in Anxiety
	Average	50.92	High in Anxiety
Highest Educational Attainment	College Graduate	51.17	High in Anxiety
	College Undergraduate	49.43	High in Anxiety
	Average	50.92	High in Anxiety

*For High, mean score is >40.77; For low, mean score is <40.77.

Table 1 shows the mean score for anxiety factor per demographic profile. For sex, males obtained a mean score of 49.69 while females obtained a mean score of 51.36. For the highest educational attainment, college graduates obtained a mean score of 51.17 while college undergraduate obtained a mean score of 49.43. The overall mean score for anxiety is 50.92. All computed mean scores across demographic profiles are greater than the baseline score of 40.77 which means it is interpreted as high in anxiety.

Table 2. Mean Score for Job Dissatisfaction Factor per Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variables	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	54.08	High Job Dissatisfaction
	Female	56.08	High Job Dissatisfaction
	Average	55.55	High Job Dissatisfaction
Highest Educational Attainment	College Graduate	55.14	High Job Dissatisfaction
	College Undergraduate	58.00	High Job Dissatisfaction
	Average	55.55	High Job Dissatisfaction

*For High, mean score is >44.00; For low, mean score is <44.00

Table 2 illustrates the mean score for job dissatisfaction factor per demographic profile. For sex, males obtained a mean score of 54.08 while females obtained a mean score of 56.08. For the highest educational attainment, college graduates obtained a mean score of 55.14 while college undergraduate obtained a mean score of 58.00. The overall mean score for Job Dissatisfaction is 55.55. All computed mean scores across demographic profiles are greater than the baseline score of 44.00 which means it is interpreted as high in job dissatisfaction.

Table 3. Mean Score for Financial Instability Factor per Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variables	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	47.08	High Financial Instability
	Female	53.94	High Financial Instability
	Average	52.12	High Financial Instability
Highest Educational Attainment	College Graduate	52.57	High Financial Instability
	College Undergraduate	49.43	High Financial Instability
	Average	52.12	High Financial Instability

*For High, mean score is >42.56; For low, mean score is <42.56

Table 3 presents the mean score for the financial instability factor per demographic profile. For sex, males obtained a mean score of 47.08 while females obtained a mean score of 53.94. For the highest educational attainment, college graduates obtained a mean score of 52.57 while college undergraduate obtained a mean score of 49.43. The overall mean score for Financial Instability is 52.12. All computed mean scores across demographic profiles are greater than the baseline score of 42.56 which interprets high in financial instability.

Table 4. Mean Score for Social Relationship Factor per Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variables	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	58.15	High Problems in Social Relationships
	Female	62.72	High Problems in Social Relationships
	Average	61.51	High Problems in Social Relationships
Highest Educational Attainment	College Graduate	61.24	High Problems in Social Relationships
	College Undergraduate	63.14	High Problems in Social Relationships
	Average	61.51	High Problems in Social Relationships

*For High, mean score is >52.85; For low, mean score is <52.85

Table 4 evidences the mean score for the social relationship factor per demographic profile. For sex, males obtained a mean score of 58.15 while females obtained a mean score of 62.72. For the highest educational attainment, college graduates obtained a mean score of 61.24 while college undergraduate obtained a mean score of 63.14. The overall mean score for Social Relationship is 61.51. All computed mean scores across demographic profiles are greater than the baseline score of 52.85 which means it is interpreted as high in a social relationship.

Table 5. Mean Score for Overall Quarter Life Crisis per Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variables	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	209.00	High in Quarter Life Crisis
	Female	224.11	High in Quarter Life Crisis
	Average	220.10	High in Quarter Life Crisis
Highest Educational Attainment	College Graduate	220.12	High in Quarter Life Crisis
	College Undergraduate	220.00	High in Quarter Life Crisis
	Average	220.10	High in Quarter Life Crisis

*For High, mean score is >189.48; For low, mean score is <189.48

Table 5 presents the overall mean score for the quarter-life crisis per demographic profile. For sex, males obtained a mean score of 209.00 while females obtained a mean score of 224.11. For the highest educational attainment, college graduates obtained a mean score of 220.12 while college undergraduate obtained a mean score of 220.00. The overall mean score for the Quarter-life crisis is 220.10. All computed mean scores across demographic profiles are greater than the baseline score of 189.48 which means it is interpreted as high in a quarter-life crisis.

Table 6. Test for Significant Difference for Sex

Factor	P-value	Mean Score	Ho Decision
Anxiety	0.63	Not Significant	Accept
Job Dissatisfaction	0.62	Not Significant	Accept
Financial Instability	0.06	Not Significant	Accept
Social Relationships	0.19	Not Significant	Accept
Overall	0.12	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

Table 6 shows the test for a significant difference in the sex demographic profile. It shows the computed p-value for each factor is greater than .05 alpha level of margin of error. Hence there is no significant difference and the null hypothesis is rejected. This would mean that the difference in mean score between male and female respondents is not significantly different and they perceived the same level of high in anxiety, job dissatisfaction, financial instability, social relationships, and overall midlife crisis.

Table 7. Test for Significant Difference for Highest Educational Attainment

Factor	P-value	Mean Score	Ho Decision
Anxiety	0.76	Not Significant	Accept
Job Dissatisfaction	0.63	Not Significant	Accept
Financial Instability	0.65	Not Significant	Accept
Social Relationships	0.80	Not Significant	Accept
Overall	1.00	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

Table 7 illustrates the test for significant differences for the highest educational attainment demographic profile. It shows the computed p-value for each factor is greater than .05 alpha level of margin of error. Hence there is no significant difference and the null hypothesis is rejected. This would mean that the difference in mean score between a college graduate and college undergraduate respondents is not significantly different and they perceived the same level of high in anxiety, job dissatisfaction, financial instability, social relationships, and overall midlife crisis.

Table 8. Test for Significant Correlation

Correlated Factor	Variable	Pearson's r	Interpretation	p-value	Significance	Null Hypothesis
Anxiety	Job Dissatisfaction	0.587	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000	S	R
	Financial Instability	0.453	Low Positive Correlation	0.001	S	R
	Social Relationships	0.439	Low Positive Correlation	0.002	S	R
Job Dissatisfaction	Financial Instability	0.352	Low Positive Correlation	0.013	S	R
	Social Relationships	0.094	Negligible Correlation	0.521	NS	S
Financial Instability	Social Relationships	0.256	Negligible Correlation	0.076	NS	S

*Significant at .05 alpha level; S=Significant, NS=Not Significant, R=Reject, A=Accept

Table 9 reveals the test for correlation for all factors. For anxiety correlated to other factors, the computed Pearson's r value correlated to job dissatisfaction is 0.587 which interpreted as Moderate Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that the correlation is significant. For anxiety correlated to financial instability, the computed Pearson's r value is 0.453 which interpreted as Low Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.001 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that the correlation is significant. For anxiety correlated to social relationships, the computed Pearson's r value is 0.439 which interpreted as Low Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.002 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that the correlation is significant. This would mean that as anxiety increases, job dissatisfaction, financial instability, and problems in a social relationship also increase.

For job dissatisfaction correlated to financial stability, the computed Pearson's r value is 0.352 which interpreted as Low Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.013 which is less than .05

alpha level. This would mean that the correlation is significant. Hence, as job dissatisfaction increases financial instability also increases significantly.

For job dissatisfaction correlated to social relationships, the computed Pearson's r value is 0.094 which interpreted as Negligible Correlation with a p -value of 0.521 which is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that the correlation is not significant. For financial stability correlated to social relationships, the computed Pearson's r value is 0.256 which interpreted as Negligible Correlation with a p -value of 0.076 which is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that the correlation is not significant.

Discussion

According to the study of National Health Service (2016), women are more likely to have anxiety. Though it is lower in East Asia (2.8%, 95% CI 2.2 to 3.4) and are twice to be affected than men (female: male ratio of 1:0:1), but they are affected under the age of 35 (2.5% to 9.1%). One of its causes can be a complex interaction of biological and lifestyle factors, affecting the daily routine of the female participants and causing them distress.

The study of Rossi and Mebert (2011) reported that college undergraduates are more functioning than college graduates. As the college undergraduates only reported to have mild anxiety but are the second reported group when it comes to anxiety, in contrast to college graduates, who are more functioning, especially to the ones who recently gone to work. The researchers suggested that regardless of sex and higher educational attainment, job satisfaction can be associated with social support from intimate family members and friends. With proper income and no difficulties in finances is significant on measuring their well-being regarding job satisfaction. Recent college graduates are quite content in their job satisfaction (Evangelista et al., 2016).

According to Lythe (2012), one of three women are suffering in financial instability than one of four men. As they are hopeless to fulfill their financial goals and put themselves under pressure to prosper in their jobs. 1.7 million young professionals are in deep pressure to achieve success in their current careers to raise money for themselves and their future families. But less than a quarter of young professionals are saving up to retirement, and most of them cannot afford to do so due to the cost of living. This has forced them to borrow money from their parents from time to time (Lythe, 2012). In an article by Ha (2017), college graduates are more likely to financially struggle, hence they are willing to set aside their dream jobs for a suitable job to make ends meet.

According to Hymas (2020), women are more likely to experience Quarter Life Crisis due to personal relationships. As they feel "lock to a relationship they do not to be a part anymore". While men feel quarter life crisis more when it comes to jobs but can feel the weight of the unwanted personal relationships like women. Tauzel (2007) added that college undergraduates have a stronger social connection in contrast to the findings of this study that college undergraduates have problems in a quarter-life crisis. As they value their social relationships it comes to family, friends, and even career connections to give themselves and advantage to their future careers.

Llagas (2018) in her study stated that 87% of young professionals can develop anxiety and depression when they lack confidence and trust in themselves in their careers. As stated by Ha (2017), some young professionals are making career options to keep themselves financially afloat. More than four out of five millennials develop jealousy and anxiety to their peers whenever they check their social media accounts and is now reportedly the most stressful generation, according to an article by Perez (2018).

A clinical psychologist, Dr. Alex Fowke, in an article by Hosie (2017), "*quarter-life crisis is a period of discouragement when it comes to relationships and financial situation*". Therefore, there is a negligible correlation between financial stability and social relationships.

The researchers recommend to young professionals to explore opportunities and take chances in both their professional and private lives in ways, for future studies, to engage in qualitative aspect such as interviews, and to have an intervention-like seminar to directly impact the community at large. Hence, continuous research toward quarter-life crisis to increase awareness for people who have experienced a quarter-life crisis is encouraged.

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